

Very Virulent Infectious Bursal Disease Virus- Induced Liver Damage and Hepato- Protective Capacity of Neem (*Azadirachta Indica*) Leaf Aqueous Extracts in Cockerels

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The aim of the present work was to study the effects of aqueous extract of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf in the liver of cockerels vaccinated and/ or challenged with very virulent infectious bursal disease virus (vvIBDV) strain. Four hundred and eighty (480) day old cockerels were used and allocated into 8 groups randomly. The birds were grouped as vaccinated/ unvaccinated, challenged/ unchallenged, neem leaf treated/ untreated groups. The IBD vaccines (intermediate plus strain) were given at 14 and 28 days of age while the experimental infection using vvIBD virus was inoculated at 35 days of age and the extracts at 3.0 mg/ml were given from day old to 6 weeks old. Serum samples were collected on the last day of the neem leaf extracts administration and that was a week post vvIBDV challenge (6 weeks), and the hepato- cellular enzymatic activities of alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) were analyzed and recorded. The results obtained showed no significant difference between the vaccinated, neem leaf treated and the control groups. However, significantly higher values of ALT, AST and ALP were obtained in the vvIBDV challenged groups when compared to the control groups. Furthermore, the values obtained in those groups that were challenged but were given the extracts had significantly lower values when compared to the challenged groups alone without prior neem extract administration. These results indicate that neem leaf aqueous extracts and IBD vaccine has no hepato- toxic effects in contrast to the vvIBDV which shows a hepato- toxic evidence. Moreover, the results show a hepato- protective capacity of neem leaf against the vvIBDV-induced liver damage.

Keywords: Very virulent infectious bursal disease virus, neem leaf aqueous extracts, hepatic damage, vaccine, cockerels.

INTRODUCTION

Infectious bursal disease (IBD) also known as gumboro disease and infectious bursitis is an acute, highly contagious viral disease of young (immature) chickens (three to five weeks old) caused by the infectious bursal disease virus belonging to the genus *Avibirnavirus* (*birnavirus*) an RNA virus of the family *Birnaviridae* (Mbuko *et al.*, 2010). The virus is a non-enveloped icosahedral, bisegmented double stranded (dsRNA) virus

with a diameter of about 55-60 nm (Mittal *et al.*, 2006; Mbuko *et al.*, 2010). The disease was first discovered in 1957 in Gumboro county, Delaware, USA by Cosgrove as a result, it is often referred to as Gumboro (Cosgrove, 1962; LAH, 2004). Since its first appearance in 1962 in Gumboro county USA, IBD has been reported in the poultry industries and in concentrated poultry production areas all over the world (Mbuko, *et al.*, 2010; Butcher and Miles, 2011) causing devastating outbreaks (Sahar *et al.*, 2004; Gargees and Shareef, 2009; Aschalew *et al.*, 2005). The disease is particularly important due to high mortalities, lowered productivity among infected chickens

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(Sahar *et al.*, 2004). It is of high economic importance in Nigeria as it results in tremendous loss to poultry farmers in terms of mortality and immunosuppression (Oladele *et al.*, 2004). Outbreak of IBD has been reported in IBD vaccinated flocks (Islam *et al.*, 2008). Suboptimal humoral immune response to IBD vaccination has been observed in birds (Jeon *et al.*, 2008; Prandini *et al.*, 2008).

In present scenario, interest is renewed in herbal medicines due to its less side effects and being safer. Interest and demand is increasing to obtain more drugs from plant sources to alleviate the ailments of humankind. The use of different parts of several medicinal plants to cure specific ailments has been in vogue form.

The green medicine has been popular since ancient times being safe and multiple benefits. Neem is rich source of different compounds having medicinal properties, so drug development programme should be started utilizing the biological and medicinal properties of neem. In modern era, emphasis should be on control of diseases of human, animals and environment using non-toxic herbal products. By making quantum of research on biological and medicinal properties of neem, some of the herbal products have been prepared but still there is lot of scope in this field for better utilization of this wonder plant (Tiwari *et al.*, 2014).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The study was conducted in Sokoto, in the Poultry pen of the Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. Sokoto State is geographically located to the North Western part of Nigeria between the longitudes 4° 8'E and 6° 54'E, and latitudes 12° and 13° 58N (NPC, 2006). The state falls within two vegetation zones: the Sudan Savannah and Northern Guinea Savannah.

The climate is characterized by altering dry and wet seasons with short cold and dry period of harmattan usually accompanied by dust-laden winds and fogs which start from October and last through February. The duration and intensity of annual rain fall ranges from 60-160 days and 635-1000mm (occurring between May to October) respectively. The mean monthly temperature is generally 20-46° C, relative humidity ranges from 12-17% with the highest occurring in August (NPC, 2006).

Experimental Birds

Four hundred and eighty (480) day old cockerels for the study which were purchased from a commercial hatchery (Farm support^R) in Ibadan were used. The

experimental birds were raised for 8 weeks.

Housing and Feeding

The birds were managed on deep litter system in cleaned formalin- potassium fumigated pens. One 200 watt electric bulb was fixed to provide warmth to the birds for each of the groups with additional source of heat around the pens. The pen temperature was maintained at 33 to 35°C for 1 to 3 weeks old and 28 to 29°C for the remaining 3 to 8 weeks old. They were fed on commercial feed; chick mash (Animal care^R) for the 8 weeks but the treated water was given from day old to 6 weeks. The feed and water were provided *ad libitum*.

Biosecurity Measures

Strict biosecurity measures were taken for all the groups. Moreover, the challenged groups were separated into a different pen entirely, employing 2 well trained poultry attendants to routinely feed the birds, disinfect themselves, watering and feeding utensils as well as the environment in order to prevent the spread of microorganisms into or outside the poultry pen. Each of the attendants was responsible for particular groups of birds (unchallenged: groups A to D and challenged: groups E to H). Groups A to D were raised in the main Faculty of Veterinary Medicine poultry pen while groups E to H within a separate pen. Complete personal protective wears were used during vaccination and experimental infection which were incinerated immediately after used. At the entrance of each pen, footbath was provided containing 2% formalin and shoes were provided and hanged just at the interior side of the pens door for use specifically within the pens. At the end of the experiment, the whole pens were fumigated with formalin- potassium composition while the litter was removed and incinerated.

Preparation and Extraction of Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) leaf Aqueous Extracts

Mature green neem leaves were used for the experiment. The leaves were obtained from Shehu Kangiwa Square and a botanist from UDUS herbarium professionally identified the Neem and labelled it (UDUH/ANS/0004). The leaves were rinsed in distilled water, air dried and pulverized. The extract was prepared following the procedure reported by (Sithisarn *et al.*, 2006).

The concentration of the aqueous Neem leaf extract used was 3.0mg/ml which was administered through drinking water for 6 weeks. The choice of the concentration was based on the earlier preliminary work done on the safety margin of the extract.

Vaccine

A live IBD (intermediate plus strain) vaccine containing

Table 1: Experimental Design

Group	IBD Vaccination Status	Experimental Challenge with vvIBDV	Neem Extract Treatment
A	Unvaccinated	Unchallenged	No Extracts given
B	Vaccinated	Unchallenged	No Extracts given
C	Vaccinated	Unchallenged	3.0mg/ml Extract
D	Unvaccinated	Unchallenged	3.0mg/ml Extract
E	Unvaccinated	Challenged	No Extracts given
F	Vaccinated	Challenged	No Extracts given
G	Vaccinated	Challenged	3.0mg/ml Extract
H	Unvaccinated	Challenged	3.0mg/ml Extract

$\geq 10^3$ EID₅₀/ml was used for the study which was sourced from an Agro- Veterinary Company in Kaduna, Nigeria. The vaccination was carried out at 2 and 4 weeks of age via oral route.

Challenge IBD Virus

At day 35 the birds in groups E, F, G and H were challenged orally with 0.1ml of a live vvIBD virus containing $10^{9.76}$ CID/ml.

Experimental Design

Grouping

The 480 birds were assigned randomly into eight groups (A to H) with 60 birds per group. Group A was the negative control group and therefore, neither receive the aqueous extracts nor were they vaccinated against IBD. Group B was the positive IBD- vaccinated control group, thus, did not receive the aqueous extracts but was vaccinated against IBD.

Group C, D, G and H were treated with 3.0mg/ml of Neem leaf aqueous extracts in drinking water from day old to 6 weeks. Group C, F and G were vaccinated against IBD while D, E and H were not vaccinated against the IBD. Birds in group E, F, G and H were challenged with vvIBD virus while those in group A, B, C and D remained unchallenged.

Vaccine and Vaccination

Birds from groups B, C, F and G were vaccinated against IBD at 14 and 28 days of age with IBD intermediate plus vaccine containing $\geq 10^3$ EID₅₀/ml, 0.2ml/bird via oral route while groups A, D, E and H remained IBD-unvaccinated.

Experimental Infection

Birds from group E, F, G and H were experimentally challenged orally with 0.2ml of vvIBD virus at 35 day of age (5 week old) while A, B, C and D were not challenged.

Blood Collection

On the last day of the neem leaf extracts administration and that was a week post vvIBDV challenge (6 weeks), using 21 gauge needle and 2 ml syringe blood sample was collected directly from the heart from five birds in each group randomly and transferred into a plain test tube. The plain test tubes containing the blood samples were then allowed to stand for two hours and then centrifuged at 10062×10^6 g for 5 minutes and the sera harvested and taken immediately to laboratory.

Liver Function Test (LFT)

The hepato- cellular enzymatic activities of alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) were analyzed calorimetrically using commercial kits (IVD Dialab Company, Wiener Neudorf, Australia) following strictly the standard procedure as described by Thefeld *et al.*, (1974) and recorded.

Statistical Analysis

The results obtained were presented in tables and their standard deviations calculated.

They were further subjected to one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) at 95% confidence interval using GraphPad[®] instat software.

RESULT

Liver Function Test

At 42 days on Neem leaves aqueous extracts administration, there was no significant ($P > 0.05$) difference in the serum AST, ALT and ALP between vaccinated and unvaccinated groups (B, C, D) and the negative control (group A). Significant ($P < 0.05$) difference in the serum ALT, AST and ALP was observed amongst the vvIBDV challenged groups (E, F, G and H). Group E and F had a significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher AST, ALT and ALP values when compared to groups G and H. (Table 2)

Table 2: Effects of Neem Leaf Aqueous Extract on Liver Enzymes of 6 Weeks Old Experimental Cockerels

Group	Extract	Vaccine	Challenge	Liver Enzymes (U/l)		
				42 day old (6 week)		
				AST	ALT	ALP
A	-	-	-	182.28±13.4 ^a	5.87±0.8 ^a	328.5±14.42 ^a
B	-	+	-	187.30±14.5 ^a	4.92±0.9 ^a	337.14±15 ^a
C	+	+	-	185.9±15.0 ^a	6.0±0.9 ^a	340±30 ^a
D	+	-	-	190.0±16.2 ^a	6.2±1.1 ^a	330.15±25 ^a
E	-	-	+	407.32±25.2 ^b	15.78±2 ^b	413.0±34 ^b
F	-	+	+	402.4±26.3 ^b	14.95±2 ^b	415±35.1 ^b
G	+	+	+	240.0±20.3 ^c	8.5±1.3 ^c	339.5±29.2 ^c
H	+	-	+	245.0±21.2 ^c	7.6±1.5 ^c	338.5±25 ^c

^{la-c} Values within columns with no common superscripts differ significantly at P<0.05

DISCUSSIONS

In this study, the administration of Neem leaves aqueous extract at 3g/L from day old to 6 weeks orally in chicks revealed no significant difference in the serum AST, ALT and ALP between groups (B, C and D) when compared to the negative control group (group A). This implies that, the extract may not be toxic to the liver. However, group E and F had significantly higher values of the serum AST, ALT and ALP when compared to groups G and H. This indicates that, the vvIBDV used during the experimental challenge at 5 weeks of age had negative impacts to the liver which has the potential tendency for hepatic injury while on the other hand, the Neem leaves extract probably had a hepato- protective effects. This is because, groups G and H were also challenged with same vvIBDV but in their own case, they were on the extract. This finding agrees to the result reported by Bhanwra *et al.*, (2000) who observed that, the extract of Neem leaf offered protection against paracetamol-induced liver damage.

The elevated level of serum AST and ALT levels are attributed to the hepatic structural damage because, these enzymes are normally localised within the cytoplasm and released into circulation after cellular damage has occurred (Kumar *et al.*, 2009). It has been reported that, elevated activity of AST, ALT and ALP in plasma/ serum are indicative of cellular leakage and loss of functional integrity of the cell membrane in the liver and that their estimations are useful quantitative markers of the extent of hepatocellular damage (Lombardi *et al.*, 2008). Yanpallewar *et al.*, (2003) also reported that, Neem leaf pre-treatment stabilised the serum levels of marker enzymes of hepatic damage (AST, ALT and ALP) by inhibiting paracetamol- induced lipid peroxidation and prevented depletion of sulfhydryl groups in the hepatocytes of Albino rat at 200mg/Kg per os.

Conclusively, the neem leaf aqueous extract and IBD vaccine studied has no any deleterious effects on liver. However, very virulent IBD virus strain (vvIBDV) has negative impacts on liver, resulting in increased level of serum AST, ALT and ALP. Thus, neem leaf aqueous

extract has a hepato- protective action against the vvIBDV effects on liver. We recommend that, the extract can be used in poultry industry in case of IBD outbreaks as a therapeutic agent and further researches should be conducted on its therapeutic effects on some important diseases that affects damages the liver in poultry.

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